

Design of a Reduced Order Robust Convex Controller for Flight Control System

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Abstract : In this paper an optimal convex controller is designed to control the angle of attack of a FOXTROT aircraft. Then the order of the system model is reduced to a low-dimensional state space by using Balanced Truncation Model Reduction Technique and finally the robust stability of the reduced model of the system is tested graphically by using Kharitonov rectangle and Zero Exclusion Principle for a particular range of perturbation value. The same robust stability is tested theoretically by using Frequency Sweeping Function for robust stability.

Keywords : Convex Optimization; Model Reduction; Balanced Truncation; Robust Stability; Kharitonov Stability Criterion; Zero Exclusion Principle; Frequency Sweeping Function

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